

MICROSCOPIC PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE AND FAILURE ANALYSIS OF CARBON-FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE UNDER SHEAR LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Carbon-fiber reinforced composites are made up of three different phases. Tensile or compressive deformation in the longitudinal (fiber) orientation is controlled by the fibers, leading to a linear stress-strain response which ends abruptly when the fibers fail by tensile fracture or kinking in compression. Conversely, major non-linear deformations can develop under transverse compression or in-plane shear because deformation is controlled by the polymeric matrix and the interphase.

In this paper, first the V-notched rail shear test was used to research the mechanical properties of composite under in-plane shear loading, and the fracture surfaces of failed specimens were examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The broken samples showed a large residual shear displacement. For $[0/90]_{8s}$ cross-ply laminate V-notched beam test, the failure mode is the interactions of intralaminar and interlaminar failure. The intralaminar interfacial debonding, matrix cracking and interlaminar degradation occurs in succession. Then a representative volume element (RVE) of fiber random distribution was established, with two dominant damage mechanisms-matrix plastic deformation and interfacial debonding included in the simulation by the extended Drucker-Prager model and cohesive zone model respectively. The simulation results clearly reveal the damage process of the composites and the interactions of different damage mechanisms. It can be concluded that the in-plane shear fracture initiates as interfacial debonding and evolves as a result of interactions between interfacial debonding and matrix plastic deformation. The progressive damage process and final failure mode of in-plane shear model which are based on constitute are very consistent with the observed result under SEM of V-notched rail shear test. Also a transverse shear model was established as contrast in order to comprehensively understand the mechanical properties of composite materials under shear loading, and the progressive damage process and final failure mode of composite under transverse shear loading were researched.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon-fiber reinforced composites are made up of three different phases. Carbon fibers are stiff and brittle while polymers are compliant and may undergo considerable deformations. Composite interphase is one separate phase, with its thickness of only several tens of nanometers to one micrometer. In micromechanics, the interphase between fiber and matrix is used to transfer stress, and interphase performance play is closely linked to fiber, matrix properties and stress state [1-2].

A number of analytical studies have been conducted in this area [3-5]. Recently several finite element models, such as the representative volume element (RVE), and unit cells based on square or hexagonal fiber arrays, have been developed [6-7]. Whitcomb and Tang employed both square and hexagonal arrays to study moisture diffusion in composites with impermeable fibers [8]; Zhang et al. devised a unit cell of cross-ply laminate based on the square array to study residual thermal stresses/strains in composites [9]; Drago and Pindera discussed appropriate boundary conditions for a repeating unit cell (RUC) comprised of multiple square array unit cells and used it to predict engineering moduli of unidirectional composites [10]; the distribution of interfacial strain and thermal residual stress in unit cell of random array were studied by Ha et al. [11,12].

In this paper, the shear response was measured using the V-notched rail shear test on cross-ply laminates and the evolution of the damage during deformation and final failure mode were ascertained by SEM. Then a unit cell of fiber random distribution based on molecules random collision model is used to analyze the damage initiation and evolution process and the interactions of different damage mechanisms, with two dominant damage mechanisms-matrix plastic deformation and interfacial debonding included in the simulation. It was found that the numerical simulations were able to reproduce the complex deformation and damage mechanisms which arise under in-plane shear and transverse shear.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

The material system of the specimen is CCF300/5228A. Rectangular specimens (76mm x 19mm) were cut from $[0/90]_{8s}$ cross-ply laminate to prepare specimens for shear tests according to the specifications of the ASTM standard D5379 (Figure 1).

Figure 1: (a) V-notched beam test coupon schematic. (b) Strain gauge locations

The fracture surfaces of failed specimens were examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and through this the microscopic damage mechanism could be determined. In Figure 2, rotation of the fibers during shear loading (up to 20-30°) was evident. Also interphase debonding and matrix cracking can be seen around the rotational fibers.

Figure 2: The fracture cross-section image of V-notched beam specimen at the amplification rate of 35

For $[0/90]_{8s}$ cross-ply laminate V-notched beam test, the failure mode is the interactions of intralaminar and interlaminar failure. The interlaminar degradation on the central section upper surface of V-notched beam specimen at low amplification rate is shown in Figure 3(a), and the intralaminar failure at high amplification rate is shown in Figure 3(b).

Figure 3: SEM micrograph of the central section upper surface of V-notched beam specimen:(a) interlaminar degradation at low amplification rate. (b) intralaminar failure at high amplification rate

3 MICROSCOPIC COMPUTATIONAL MODELING

3.1 Microscopic computational model of carbon-fiber reinforced composite under in-plane shear loading

The experimental results above have demonstrated that the shear response of carbon fiber reinforced composites is rather complex due to the interaction of various deformation and damage micro-mechanisms. So FEM simulations that take into account the details of the microstructure are thus critical to understand the role played by the different factors. The modeling strategy to simulate the in-plane shear deformation of the cross-ply laminates is depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4: (a) Schematic of the simulation strategy to model the in-plane shear behavior of the cross-ply composite through the combination of loading parallel (τ_{12}^{\parallel}) and perpendicular (τ_{12}^{\perp}) to the fibers. (b) Representative volume element of the lamina microstructure.

In this paper, a model containing 25 fibers and of 56% volume fraction is adopted. The fibers are randomly embedded in the matrix, with their centers, as is shown in Figure 4(b) based on collision

algorithm. The material system of representative volume element is CCF300/5228A and the material properties of fiber and matrix used in the model are listed in Table 1.

Fiber/CCF300	
Longitudinal modulus, E_{1f} (GPa)	224.29
Transverse modulus, $E_{2f} = E_{3f}$ (GPa)	30.18
The in-plane shear modulus, $G_{12f} = G_{13f}$ (GPa)	70.64
The in-plane Poisson's ratio, $\nu_{12f} = \nu_{13f}$	0.243
Transverse shear modulus, G_{23f} (GPa)	11.52
Transverse Poisson's ratio, ν_{23f}	0.310
Matrix/5228A	
Modulus, E_m (GPa)	3.22
Poisson's ratio, ν_m	0.346

Table 1: The material properties of CCF300/5228A

The extended linear Drucker-Prager criterion is employed to predict the yielding of the polymeric matrix:

$$F = t - p \tan \beta - d = 0, \quad t = \frac{1}{2} q \left[1 + \frac{1}{K} - \left(1 - \frac{1}{K} \right) \left(\frac{r}{q} \right)^3 \right] \quad (1)$$

where p is the hydrostatic stress, q is the Mises equivalent stress, r is the third invariant of deviatoric stress, β is the slope of the linear yield surface in the p - t stress plane, d is the cohesion of the material, and k is the ratio of the yield stress in triaxial tension to the yield stress in triaxial compression and, thus, introduces different yield behaviors between tension and compression.

The ductile criterion is used to predict the onset of damage for the matrix. After the onset of failure, the damage evolution is controlled by the fracture energy which is given as

$$G_f = \int_{\bar{\varepsilon}_0^{pl}}^{\bar{\varepsilon}_f^{pl}} L \sigma_y d\bar{\varepsilon}^{pl} = \int_0^{\bar{u}_f^{pl}} \sigma_y d\bar{u}^{pl} \quad (2)$$

L is a characteristic length, associated with an integration point.

The material parameters of the matrix are shown in Table 2. And the equivalent plastic strains at the onset of damage for uniaxial tension and compression are set as 0.05 and 0.5, respectively [13].

The interphase in this paper uses cohesive element defined in terms of the bi-linear traction-separation law. Quadratic nominal stress criterion is used to simulate the initial damage which can be represented as:

$$\left\{ \frac{\langle t_n \rangle}{t_n^0} \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{t_s}{t_s^0} \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{t_t}{t_t^0} \right\}^2 = 1 \quad (3)$$

$$\langle t_n \rangle = \begin{cases} t_n & t_n > 0 \\ 0 & t_n < 0 \end{cases}, \quad t_i^0 \quad (i = n, s, t) \text{ is the interphase strength parameters.}$$

The power law criterion states that failure under mixed-mode conditions is governed by a power law interaction of the energies required to cause failure in the individual (normal and two shear) modes.

The material parameters of the interphase based on traction-separation law are shown in Table 2.

$d(\text{MPa})$	β	k	$G_m(\text{J/m}^2)$
64.7	24°	0.8	0.5
$K_n=K_s=K_t(\text{GPa/m})$	$t_n^0 = t_s^0 = t_t^0 (\text{Mpa})$	$G_n=G_s=G_t(\text{J/m}^2)$	
10^8	39.1	100	

Table 2: Material parameters of the matrix and interphase

$G_i^c (i = n, s, t)$ is the critical fracture energy required to cause failure in the normal, the first, and the second shear directions.

The boundary conditions are combination of loading parallel (τ_{12}^{\parallel}) and perpendicular (τ_{12}^{\perp}) to the fibers for in-plane shear model: one boundary surface of the unit cell which is parallel to the fiber direction and another one which is perpendicular to the fiber axis are clamped in one direction, and a pair of shear loading which is parallel to the clamped direction was applied on the opposite two boundary surfaces until final fracture happens.

FEM models are generated in ABAQUS/Explicit. Fibers and matrix are meshed with 8-node linear brick reduced integration elements (C3D8R) with hourglass control, and a very thin layer of 8-node three-dimensional cohesive elements (COH3D8) are inserted between each fiber and the surrounding matrix to simulate the interfacial debonding.

3.2 Microscopic computational model of carbon-fiber reinforced composite under transverse shear loading

In order to comprehensively understand the mechanical properties of composite materials under shear loading, a transverse shear model is established as contrast. As the same with in-plane shear model, a fiber random distribution model containing 25 fibers and of 56% volume fraction is adopted. And constitute material properties are all same.

The boundary conditions for transverse shear model are as follows: Two adjacent boundary surfaces of the unit cell which are parallel to the fiber direction are clamped in one direction, and a pair of shear loading which is parallel to the clamped direction was applied on the opposite two boundary surfaces until final fracture happens.

4 RESULTS AND DISSCUSSION

4.1 Microscopic progressive damage analysis of in-plane shear model

The stress-strain curve of representative volume element under in-plane shear loading is shown in Figure 5. An apparent non-linear plastic deformation can be seen from the curve.

Figure 5: The stress-strain curve of RVE under in-plane shear loading

In order to explore the damage initiation and evolution process of fiber-reinforced composite under a particular load, characteristic points on stress-strain curve are selected to reveal the microscopic failure mechanism, combining with the corresponding damage state in analysis, as in Figure 6. At point A, interfacial debonding is the only form of damage, and debonding locates in two-pole position of the fiber. Point B is the second point of the curve, and at this point the matrix cracking occurs in the vicinity of interphase debonding region. Point C corresponds to the final state of destruction. Interfacial debonding and matrix cracking further extend with matrix crack cross-linking, and finally a main crack occurs, resulting in the ultimate destruction. This is the strength of in-plane shear model.

Figure 6: Damage initiation and evolution under in-plane shear loading

4.2 Microscopic progressive damage analysis of transverse shear model

The stress-strain curve of representative volume element under transverse shear loading is shown in Figure 7, illustrating that the transverse shear strength is lower than the in-plane shear strength.

Figure 7: The stress-strain curve of RVE under transverse shear loading

Also at point A interfacial debonding is the only form of damage but it mainly occurs at the direction of $\pm 45^\circ$. After point A, matrix initial damage occurs. Quite apparent matrix cracking can be observed near the interphase debonding zone when stress-strain curve reaches point B. It also shows that the composite transverse shear strength is controlled by matrix more. Finally at point C, the matrix

cracks at different locations are linked to form a main crack-the plastic shear band, passing through the interphase cracks, as shown in Figure 8C.

(A) interface debonding (B) matrix plastic damage (C) the final state of transverse shear failure
Figure 8: Damage initiation and evolution under transverse shear loading

5 CONCLUSIONS

The V-notched rail shear test was used to research the mechanical properties of composite under in-plane shear loading, and the fracture surfaces of failed specimens were examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The broken samples showed a large residual shear displacement, typical of a very ductile fracture process. For $[0/90]_{8s}$ cross-ply laminate V-notched beam test, the failure mode is the interactions of intralaminar and interlaminar failure. The intralaminar interfacial debonding, matrix cracking and interlaminar degradation occurs in succession.

A computational micromechanical analysis has been carried out to study the microscopic failure mechanisms of composite under shear loading. The simulation results clearly reveal the microscopic failure mechanisms of the composites. Under in-plane shear, with the increase of load, interfacial debonding first occurs at the two-pole position of the fibers where the inter-fiber distances are small, and then matrix plastic damage happens at the vicinity of the interfacial debonding; then, interfacial debonding and matrix cracking further extend with matrix crack cross-linking, and a main crack occurs, resulting in the ultimate destruction.

In case of transverse shear, the transverse shear strength is lower than the in-plane shear strength. Interfacial debonding first occurs at the direction of $\pm 45^\circ$, and then matrix initial damage occurs. Quite apparent matrix cracking can be observed near the interphase debonding zone. It also shows that the composite transverse shear strength is controlled by matrix more. Finally, the matrix cracking at different locations are linked to form a main crack-the plastic shear band, passing through the interphase cracks and resulting in completely failure of the composite.

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